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Interaction-Based Study of Kaempferol and P47^{phox}

Habib Eslami¹, Koosha Rokhzadi², Seyed Parsa Golshani², Mohamad Bagher Khademerfan²,
Kaveh Haji-Allahverdipoor^{2*}

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Molecular Medicine Research Center, Hormozgan Health Institute, Hormozgan University of Medicinal Sciences, Bandar Abbas, Iran

² Cellular and Molecular Research Center, Research Institute for Health Development, Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences, Sanandaj, Iran

Abstract

Background and aim: Excessive intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) are implicated in neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's, ALS, and Parkinson's. ROS contribute to neuronal dysfunction and death, necessitating novel strategies to inhibit their production. NADPH oxidase (NOX) and its regulatory subunit p47^{phox} are critical in ROS formation. Inhibition of p47^{phox}, particularly through small molecules, presents a potential therapeutic approach. Kaempferol, a polyphenolic antioxidant, has shown efficacy as a NOX inhibitor by binding to p47^{phox} and reducing ROS.

Materials and Methods: This study employs in silico techniques to explore kaempferol's binding mechanism with p47^{phox}. Using homology modelling, docking, molecular dynamics simulations, and free energy calculations, we identified key interactions between kaempferol and the p47^{phox} subunit.

Results: Results indicate that kaempferol interacts strongly with the wild-type p47^{phox}, particularly with residues Trp193 and Cys196, forming stable complexes and maintaining significant binding affinity. Mutations at these residues (W193R/C196A) reduce binding affinity and protein flexibility, highlighting their importance in the interaction.

Conclusion: These findings suggest that kaempferol, by targeting p47^{phox}, could be a potent inhibitor of NOX-mediated neurodegeneration.

Keywords: *Kaempferol, NADPH oxidase, p47^{phox}, Neuroprotection, Molecular dynamics*

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*Corresponding authors:

Kaveh Haji-Allahverdipoor
Cellular and Molecular Research
Center, Research Institute for
Health Development, Kurdistan
University of Medical Sciences,
Sanandaj, Iran.

E-mail address:

Allahverdipoorkaveh@gmail.com

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Introduction

Excessive and unabated intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation are common denominators in many neurodegenerative diseases [1], [2]. There is mounting evidence pointing to ROS as a crucial mediator of neuronal dysfunction and apoptotic death in the course of these diseases [3], [4]. Currently, antioxidants seem neither to offer sufficient specificity nor appropriate robustness to ameliorate neurodegeneration. Thus, finding novel strategies to inhibit ROS production is necessary and might be helpful in preventing or reversing the deterioration of the brain [5], [6]. Among several signaling pathways leading to neuronal death, considerable attention has been paid to some of the regulatory subunits of NADPH oxidase (NOX), especially p47^{phox} [7]. This subunit, along with other cytosolic subunits such as p40^{phox} and p67^{phox}, as well as membrane-associated gp91^{phox} (NOX2) and p22^{phox} subunits, comprise the multisubunit structure of NOX2 isoform [8], [9]. NOX subunit assembly starts after the phosphorylation of p47^{phox} by various kinases, including p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) [10], [11]. The activated enzyme complex produces ROS, which is essential for host defence against microbial invasion. However, inappropriate and sustained activation of NOX2 results in apoptotic neuronal loss in neurodegenerative processes [1], [5]. Hence, over the past decade, in order to attenuate the exaggerated NOX activity, many efforts have been undertaken to design specific inhibitors targeting different stages and components in the process of NOX activation [6], [12], [13]. Among them, small molecular inhibitors for p47^{phox} have been proposed to be potentially beneficial in protecting against neurodegeneration [14], [15]. Kaempferol is a polyphenol antioxidant found in fruits and vegetables. At the molecular level, kaempferol has been reported to modulate a number of key elements in cellular signal transduction pathways linked to apoptosis, angiogenesis, inflammation, and metastasis [16], [17]. Additionally, kaempferol has been identified as a NOX inhibitor since it inhibits NOX by directly binding to p47^{phox} and decreases NOX-mediated ROS formation [18]. Thus, it has been suggested that kaempferol may be a potent prophylactic against NOX-mediated neurodegeneration [15]. Given this broad experimental efficiency observed for kaempferol, understanding its mechanisms of action is very important. It will assist in developing and testing more powerful and effective analogues. Until now, many molecular targets have been identified, which potentially underlies its putative cytoprotective properties [17]. In this study, we used powerful computational tools [19] including homology modelling, computational docking, in silico mutation analysis, molecular dynamics simulations, and free energy calculations to determine how kaempferol interacts with p47^{phox}.

Material and Methods

- *Molecular Modelling and Docking*

The entire full protein structure was constructed using corresponding PDB structures in the RCSB PDB databank (1KQ6, 1NG2, 1K4U) by MODELLER 9.17 software [20]. An optimized structural model of p47^{phox} was finally obtained by energy minimization. In order to find a plausible binding conformation between p47^{phox} and kaempferol, we carried out automatic molecular docking using AutoDockTools 1.5.6 [21].

- *Molecular Dynamics Simulations*

MD simulations of two systems, wild-type and double mutant (W193A/C196A) p47^{phox}-kaempferol complexes, were performed using GROMACS 5.1.2 package [22] with CHARMM36 force field [23]. Molecular dynamic simulations were conducted in the following order according to Haji-Allahverdipoor, Jalali Javaran [24], using gmx pdb2gmx, gmx solvate, gmx genion, gmx grompp and gmx mdrun GROMACS modules in distinct steps with comprehensive output files

evaluations after each step. The utilities of GROMACS were used to analyze MD simulation trajectories. Complementary analyses were conducted by utilizing UCSF chimera [25] and XMGrace software [26], respectively. Binding free energies were estimated using the Molecular Mechanics Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MMPBSA) method [27]. MMPBSA is a computational method to estimate the binding free energy between two molecules, such as in a protein-ligand complex. In MMPBSA, the force field plays a crucial role in the estimation of the binding free energy, which is a suitable measure for the evaluation of binding affinity between two molecules in a complex. Calculations are conducted via comparison of energy levels of protein, ligand, or any of the components in solution state with the energy level of the complex in solution. The differences in energy levels could be used to estimate the binding affinity.

Results

The binding pocket was formed by coils, turns, beta sheets, and bends of the N-terminal SH3A domain (Figure 1G&H). Hydrogen bonds are essential for affinity and specificity in protein-ligand complexes. The MD results show that the wild-type p47^{phox} was able to maintain three H bonds with kaempferol in the binding site most of the time and achieved six in some moments, whereas in the mutant structure, it oscillated between none and one H bond (Figure 1I). In the following process, to verify the stability of the kaempferol-p47^{phox} complex, the root mean square deviation (RMSD) was calculated. Protein flexibility allows increased affinity to be achieved between a drug and its target (Figure 2A) [28]. Thus, the dynamic behavior of all residues was analyzed by means of root mean square fluctuation (RMSF).

Figure 1. Illustration of p47^{phox} functional domains (A). Ramachandran plot for structural analysis of the p47^{phox} protein model (B). Kaempferol (C) interacts with the potential binding pocket on p47^{phox}, which is highlighted in yellow (D). Interaction plot of kaempferol with the wild-type (E) and W193R/C196A mutant form of p47^{phox} (F) using average structure by the program LIGPLOT v.4.5.3. Dotted green lines

represent hydrogen bonds. The red arc with spokes shows hydrophobic contacts. The time evolution of the secondary structure (DSSP classification) for the wild-type and W193R/C196A mutant protein are shown in panels G and H, respectively. The number of hydrogen bonds formed between kaempferol and p47^{phox} protein during MD simulation (I).

More degree of flexibility was observed in the wild than the mutant p47^{phox} throughout the simulation time (Figure 2B). The mutation caused a significant reduction in the flexibility of the SH3A domain (residues 156–214), which is the putative binding site for kaempferol and also interacts with the p22^{phox} during NOX activation. The conformational flexibility of protein at ligand binding residues enables it to interact better with ligands than a rigid conformation. Thus, the loss of flexibility of the majority of amino acids that participated in the drug binding pocket of the W193R/C196A mutant signifies the loss of binding affinity with kaempferol. Furthermore, we examined the density of the system as a function of a specified box vector. The average atomic density of the W193R/C196A mutant was 27.7 nm, while this value for the wild-type was 15.4 (Figure 2C&D). Effects of W193R/C196A mutation on conformational geometry were observed by analysis of radius of gyration (Rg), solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), and protein intramolecular hydrogen bonds plots. The mutant structure revealed a lower degree of variation and lower Rg values compared to the wild-type protein, confirming that it acquired a more rigid and compact conformation (Figure 2E). Due to the compactness, the mutant structure also showed fewer values of SASA (Figure 2F). The SASA plots well support the major structural transition found between 0 and 50ns in the Rg plot. Overall, the higher values of SASA and Rg indicate that wild p47^{phox} adopts an expanded conformation during MD simulation. The higher prevalence of protein intramolecular hydrogen bonds in the mutant structure than in the wild-type also obviously indicates the rigidity of its structure (Figure 2G).

It is well known that the number of secondary structural elements determines the structural flexibility of a protein molecule. The results of DSSP analysis (Figure 1G &H) showed that the secondary structural elements, such as β -sheet and α -helix, which are rigid in nature, dominated the mutant structure compared to the wild-type during simulation. To gain further insight into the conformational changes, correlations between the dynamic motions of the intra- and inter-domains of p47^{phox} were quantified through the dynamic cross-correlation matrix (DCCM) [29]. In comparison with the wild-type p47^{phox} (Figure 2H), both positive and negative correlative motions were found to weaken in the mutant structure (Figure 2I).

This result suggests that mutation decreases the residue motions, and the protein acquires rigid conformation. Moreover, more positive correlative motions were noticed in the SH3A domain (residues 156–214) of the wild-type structure, which is well supported by the RMSF plot. In the RMSF plot, the residue position from 156 to 214 showed more flexibility than the mutant structure (Figure 2B). This region was considered as the potential binding site for kaempferol in this study. Altogether, as a result of W193R/C196A mutations, the structure becomes more rigid conformation and interacts unfavorably with kaempferol than the wild-type p47^{phox}, which is evident from RMSF, density map, Rg, SASA, protein intramolecular hydrogen bonds, DSSP and DCCM analysis.

Figure 2. The α RMSD (A) and RMSF (B) plots of $p47^{phox}$ protein. The protein density plot of wild-type (C) and W193R/C196A mutant (D) forms of $p47^{phox}$. The plot of R_g (E) and SASA (F) of α atoms of $p47^{phox}$. The number of protein intra-molecular hydrogen bonds formation (G). Cross-correlation matrix of the fluctuations of coordinates for α atoms around their mean positions during the MD simulation: Cyan represents positive correlations, whereas magenta represents negative correlations. The domain regions are labeled, and the extent of motions are color-coded, (H) wild type and (I) mutant $p47^{phox}$.

- Structural and Docking Analysis of the Interaction Between $p47^{phox}$ and Kaempferol

The stereochemical quality of the structural model of full $p47^{phox}$ protein (Figure 1A) was analyzed by a Ramachandran plot (Figure 1B), which indicates that 99.7% of all residues are in preferred regions with the exception of one outlier (0.3%). Despite a wealth of knowledge pertaining to the functional role of $p47^{phox}$, the binding site of small molecule $p47^{phox}$ inhibitors, such as apocynin, has not been well defined in the literature. Based on previously reported experimental mutagenesis results [7], [14], [30], we were able to suggest a binding site that was approximately around Trp193 and Cys196 within the $p47^{phox}$ N-terminal SH3A domain, a domain that has been shown to interact with $p22^{phox}$ during NOX activation. Kaempferol was docked into the putative binding pocket of the wild-type and W193R/C196A mutant proteins. The wild-type protein displayed stronger affinity ($\Delta G = -8.01$ kcal/mol, $K_i = 4.0\mu M$) to minocycline than that of the mutated $p47^{phox}$ ($\Delta G = -7.15$ kcal/mol, $K_i = 7.0\mu M$) in the molecular docking analysis. To confirm docking results and to understand the dynamic behavior of the complex, the best conformation of the $p47^{phox}$ -kaempferol complex obtained from docking was subjected to molecular dynamic (MD) simulations. The conformational ensembles of protein structures were studied by principal component analysis (PCA) to obtain a broader view of the change in the collective motion of protein [31]. The projection of the first two eigenvectors, containing the maximum motions, in

conformational space for wild-type and mutant proteins was done (Figure 3A). The results demonstrated that in comparison with the wild-type structure, the clusters of W193R/C196A mutant were well-defined, occupied less area in space and showed narrow variations in the conformational motion along the first two principal components, thereby demonstrating its rigidity and compactness. At the same time, the wild-type form of p47^{phox} was expanded in the conformational space due to its flexibility. To examine the sub-conformational structural transitions in p47^{phox} and kaempferol complexes, we studied the Gibbs free energy landscape (FEL) [32] against the first two principal components, namely PC1 and PC2, which describes how protein's free energy correlates with the three-dimensional arrangement of the molecule. Figure 3 represents 2D and 3D views of the FEL analysis and ΔG value 0 to 19.3 and 16.8kJ/mol for wild and mutant, respectively. The global energy minima conformations were designated by blue color. The size and shape of the minimal energy area indicate the stability of a complex. Since the thermodynamically most stable structure resides in a minimum on the free-energy (ΔG) surface, smaller and more concentrated blue areas suggest more stability of the corresponding complex during MD simulation [33]. The wild type showed more centralized and concentrated minima (in 2D) or a single minimum energy basin (in 3D) (Figure 3B), whereas the mutant displayed three energy basins separated by a low-energy barrier (Figure 3C). This indicates that compared with the wild type, the mutant p47^{phox}-kaempferol complex is not thermodynamically stable and thus switches to various conformations to achieve minima.

Figure 3. Projection of C α atoms of wild-type and W193R/C196A mutant structures of p47^{phox} in phase space along the eigenvector 1 and 2 (A). Gibbs Free energy landscape (FEL) of p47^{phox} (B) and its mutant (C) along the two principal eigenvectors. The blue region depicts conformations with lower energy; the yellow color signifies the meta-stable states, and the red corresponds to conformations having high energy. The representative protein conformations in the minimum energy basin are shown in the cartoon representation. Energy comparisons of the key residues differently contribute to the binding free energies between kaempferol and the wild-type mutant forms of p47^{phox} protein (D).

The effects of mutations (W193R/C196A) in p47^{phox} on the binding affinity of kaempferol were

examined by calculating the binding free energies (ΔG_{bind}) using the MM-PBSA approach. The detailed energetic items for ΔG_{bind} are listed in Table 1. We found that the predicted ΔG_{bind} value for kaempferol interaction with the wild-type protein was substantially more negative than the mutant one, thus implying a higher binding affinity of kaempferol to the wild-type protein. The high binding affinity obtained from the analysis of MD trajectories reflects a longer residence time for the ligand at its binding site and enhanced favorable interactions as well. Here, among the energy items involved in ΔG_{bind} , the van der Waals interactions were the dominant force facilitating the binding. In the case of mutant p47^{phox}, these interactions also contribute the most to ΔG_{bind} , and the loss of binding affinity of kaempferol originated mainly from their weakening after the W193R/C196A mutations in amino acid residues. The ΔG_{bind} was decomposed into single-residue contributions to define the key residues in p47^{phox} interacting with minocycline (Figure 3D). In wild-type p47^{phox}, Cys196 was a key residue for the binding with kaempferol, resulting in the free energy difference of about -9.02 kJ/mol due to the formation of H-bond.

Table 1. Components of the MM/PBSA binding free energy calculated for wild and mutant p47^{phox}-kaempferol complexes.

p47 ^{phox} form	Van der Waal energy (kJ/mol)	Electrostatic energy (kJ/mol)	Polar solvation energy (kJ/mol)	SASA energy (kJ/mol)	Total binding energy (kJ/mol)
Wild	-155.587	-23.511	117.636	-14.806	-76.267
W193R/C196A	-75.62	-10.58	63.573	-6.23	-28.857

The other main contributing residues for kaempferol binding were Val149, Thr160, Tyr161, Tyr167, Val185, Trp193, and Trp194, which interacted by van der Waals forces. However, Ala196 and Arg193 had small free energy decomposition for mutants as compared with the wild type, thus demonstrating poor interaction of mutant p47^{phox} with kaempferol.

Discussion

Generally, p47^{phox} plays a critical role in the NOX2 complex in cooperation with p40^{phox}, p67^{phox} and p22^{phox} that triggered NOX-mediated neurodegeneration. Kaempferol is a critical inhibitor of p47^{phox} that suppresses neurodegeneration (Figure 4). This study, which aims to discern which functional domains in p47^{phox} protein might bind with kaempferol, was performed in silico analyses based on previous experimental clues [34]. After the assessment of the preliminary studies [14], [35], [36] and merging their results, the map of interaction sites was estimated to define the box type for conducting precise molecular docking.

Figure 4. Mechanistic model of neuroprotection mediated by kaempferol against NOX-induced ROS generation.

These results suggest that Trp193 and Cys196 are the most plausible ligand-binding residues in the SH3 tandem of p47^{phox}, and their blockade by drug molecules might weaken the interaction between p47^{phox} and p22^{phox}; Therefore, the docking grid was defined as such to include these residues in the potential binding pocket for molecular docking analysis between p47^{phox} and kaempferol. The binding affinity ($\Delta G = -8.01$ kcal/mol, $K_i = 4.0\mu\text{M}$) calculated after docking for the complex in which kaempferol binds to both Trp193 and Cys196 was in the range of the experimentally IC_{50} for neuroprotection ($5.0\text{-}100\mu\text{M}$) in cell culture models of neurotoxicity [15], indicating that the predicted binding pocket for kaempferol is likely to be valid. In fact, the chemical structure of kaempferol partially accounts for this high affinity for binding to p47^{phox} and favorable interaction. Cyclic quinones such as trimer hydroxylated quinone (IIIHyQ) can easily bind to -SH moiety present in the cysteine residues via Michael adducts [14]. Kaempferol displays topological organization comparable to cyclic quinones and contains a Michael acceptor moiety. Therefore, kaempferol as a quinone-like compound can interact with Cys196 residue by Michael addition. The molecular docking results illustrated that kaempferol forms Van der Waals and hydrogen bonds with both Trp193 and Cys196, which provides stabilization of the ligand in the binding pocket. Aside from these interactions, Trp193 also engages in a hydrophobic π -stacking interaction with the aromatic rings of kaempferol. Since the interactions between the PRR of p22^{phox} and the N-SH3 domain of p47^{phox} occur through Van der Waals and hydrogen bond interactions, it is highly probable that small molecules that have similar interactions with the p47^{phox} residues responsible for binding to p22^{phox} can disrupt the association of these two NOX2 subunits [14]. When Trp193 and Cys196 were mutated to arginine and alanine, respectively, the predicted affinity obtained from molecular docking decreased ($\Delta G = -7.15$ kcal/mol, $K_i = 7.0\mu\text{M}$). Thus, in silico mutation analysis suggests that the lack of Cys196 and Trp193 in the binding site dramatically decreases the binding affinity of kaempferol to p47^{phox}. This is due to the structural changes that p47^{phox} has undergone following amino acid substitution, which seems to interfere with favorable interactions between kaempferol and p47^{phox}. This deduction was supported by molecular dynamic simulations and comparing binding free energies between p47^{phox} and kaempferol in the wild-type and mutant forms. The binding free energy binding difference ($\Delta\Delta G$) in the ligand interactions between the mutant and the wild-type form of p47^{phox} was 47.41 kJ/mol.

Table 1 illustrates the contributions of the individual energy terms (calculated by the MM-PBSA approach) to the total energy. In the wild type, the Van der Waal contribution was -155.587 kJ/mol, while the Electrostatic contribution was -23.511 kJ/mol. Thus, the calculated free energy of binding ΔG_{bind} was -76.267 kJ/mol. In the case of mutant p47^{phox}, this value decreases to -28.857 kJ/mol. According to these calculations, kaempferol binds stronger to the wild than to the mutant type, and this is due to its closer contact with Trp193 and Cys196. The van der Waals interactions were about five times higher than the electrostatic ones in both wild and mutant forms due to the prevalent steric contacts of kaempferol with the hydrophobic residues in the active site.

Conclusion

In agreement with the previously reported mutagenesis experiments, the in-silico analysis carried out in this study has pinpointed several key amino acid residues of p47^{phox}, including Trp193 and Cys196 located in the N-terminal tandem SH3-domain, that may be engaged in the interaction with kaempferol and forming the potential ligand-binding pocket. Following binding to p47^{phox}, kaempferol might interfere with NOX complex assembly by attenuating the interaction between p47^{phox} and p22^{phox}. Additionally, the results suggest that kaempferol interferes with the activation of p47^{phox} through the inhibition of its phosphorylation after binding and the subsequent stabilization of its inactive state.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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